

Column Chromatographic Separation of Hydrogen Sulphide using Silica Gel coated with Metal Salts

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Column chromatography is a well established separation technique useful for the analysis of cations. Nevertheless the method is not popular for separation of gas pollutants. The present communication describes the usefulness of metal salt coated silica gel for the quantitative analysis of hydrogen sulphide.

Results and Discussion

To study the metal salt required for coating on the silica gel, its amount was varied from 1 to 100 mg/10 g of silica gel. It was noted that 1 mg/10 g of silica gel could retain hydrogen sulphide quantitatively. For practical purposes, generally 5 mg of metal salt were utilised. Fe, Cu, Pb, Ni and Cr were studied as coating materials. Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} and Pb retained H₂S quantitatively using both the methods of coating, whereas Cu could only retain H₂S quantitatively with method (i). Coating with method (ii) was found to be unsuitable for Cu, Cr and Ni owing to their poor retention values on a silica gel column. Thus, these metals were not coated on a silica gel. The elution studies of H₂S from the column were carried out using HNO₃, HCl and NaOH from Pb^{II}, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} coated silica gel. It was possible to elute hydrogen sulphide from the lead-coating with 1–2 M HCl and HNO₃, Fe^{III}-coating with 4 M HCl and 2 M HNO₃ and Fe^{II}-coating with 0.5–2.0 M HCl and HNO₃.

The study shows that pre-coated silica gel can be used to quantitatively retain sulphide from various sources.

Experimental

Amil (India) colorimeter was used. A Pyrex chromatographic column (7 mm dia × 30 cm) was used with glass wool plug at the bottom.

A fresh solution of standard H₂S was prepared by dissolving Na₂S.9H₂O (0.127 g; AnalaR) in distilled and demineralised water (100 ml) obtained by ion-exchange resin and standardised iodometrically¹. It contained 200 mg ml⁻¹ of hydrogen sulphide. A solution containing 50 μg ml⁻¹ was prepared by an appropriate dilution. Bromopyrogallol red (BPR) 0.025%, 1% ammonium acetate, 1,10-phenanthroline, gelatin, silver nitrate and EDTA (all AnalaR) were used. Silica gel (B.D.H.; 100–200 mesh) was dried at 20° for 2 h. The coating of metal salt on silica gel was carried out by two methods: (i) Known quantity of silica gel was soaked in metal salt (20 ml), then washed with water and the metal coated silica gel was packed into the column, and (ii) Metal salt solution (20 ml) was passed through the silica gel column (bed-height ~ 10 cm) at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹, then washed with water and the metal was retained on the column as a coating.

The solution containing 50 μg of hydrogen sulphide was passed through the silica gel column at the flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. Hydrogen sulphide was retained on the column and the effluent was tested for the presence of hydrogen sulphide spectrophotometrically as its ternary complex of silver

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phenanthroline bromopyrogallol red at 640 nm². Hydrogen sulphide was stripped from the column with mineral acids (HNO₃/HCl). Ten fractions (each 2 ml) were collected and hydrogen sulphide from each fraction was determined photometrically.

References

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